

**DEVELOPMENTAL SUPERVISION PRACTICES ON CLASSROOM
OBSERVATIONS OF SCHOOL HEADS**

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Abstract

Developmental supervision is an approach to teacher supervision that focuses on improving the quality of instruction. It involves using ongoing formative assessment to help teachers recognize and develop their strengths, as well as to identify areas for improvement. The purpose of the study was to explore the Developmental Supervision Practices of School Heads on Classroom Observations as a platform for determining the best practices that motivate, support, and improve the performance of teachers in the effective delivery of instruction. It investigated the strengths and weaknesses including the issues and concerns of School Heads in classroom observations. The researchers inquired into the educational theories and related studies to look closely at the concerns of School Heads as to classroom observation. This study employed descriptive–correlational research design. Descriptive correlational design is used in research studies that aim to provide static pictures of situations as well as establish the relationship between different variables. Furthermore, the correlational study involved three variables such as the level of implementation of developmental supervision practices, teachers’ performance, and learners’ performance will be studied to establish their relationship. Areas of classroom supervision like planning and preparations, organizational and implementation post-instructional supervision will be patterned with the Styles of developmental supervision such as directive, non-directive, and correlational which are all anchored on the RPMS Standards on Classroom Observations. The study recruited 280 elementary School Heads of the Schools Division of Ilocos Sur and Balanga City. Simple random sampling was used to select the respondents. Mean was used to determine the instructional supervisory practices of schools. Frequency and percentage were used to rate teachers and students. Pearson r correlation was used to assess the association between supervision (directive, collaborative, and nondirective approaches) and teacher and student performance. Quantitative findings showed that most responders had good instructional supervision. Teachers and students performed well. Instructional supervisory effectiveness indirectly influences teachers and students. Participants' narratives revealed six themes. After integrating both strands, three overarching themes emerged: seamless use of technology for excellent education, performance is boosted via professional development, and collaboration from all stakeholders to help teachers and learners.

Keywords: Supervision Practices, Descriptive-Correlation, School Heads, Classroom Observations, RPMS Standards

Introduction

The importance of a study on the developmental supervision practices on classroom observations of School Heads cannot be overstated. As the leader of a school, the school principal is responsible for fostering a positive, collaborative learning environment for students and staff alike (Cole et al., 2021). Classroom observations are an important tool in assessing the quality of teaching and learning taking place in classrooms, and it is the school principal's job to ensure that the observations are conducted in a constructive and effective manner. Developmental supervision practices are a form of instructional leadership and are designed to support teachers in their professional growth and development by providing feedback and guidance (Lang, 2019). Through this type of supervision, school principals can help teachers refine their practice and build their understanding of best practices.

Additionally, classroom observations provide valuable data that can be used to inform and improve instructional practices, assess the impact of interventions, and evaluate the effectiveness of instructional strategies. Therefore, a study on the developmental supervision practices on classroom observations of School Heads is critical to ensure that school principals are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to conduct effective, meaningful classroom observations. Such a study will also provide valuable insight into the impact of instructional leadership on the quality of teaching and learning, as well as the effectiveness of instructional strategies.

School heads have long observed and supervised classrooms (Rahabav, 2016). It ensures that instructors are giving kids the greatest teaching and that the school is fulfilling its educational objectives. These practices' global efficacy is disputed. School heads worry that classroom surveillance and supervision might hinder learning. It may criticize instructors and make the school unpleasant. This may hurt teaching and staff morale. Thus, some school heads choose positive feedback and assessment over these methods. Some School Heads think that classroom monitoring and supervision are necessary to ensure that instructors are teaching well, and students are learning well. It can highlight areas for improvement and assist struggling instructors. It may also help school heads comprehend the teaching and learning process and make better policy choices.

Philippine school principals observe classes. It ensures teachers perform well and learners get the education they need. School heads may assess staff performance via classroom observation supervision (Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021). Supervising classroom observation begins with determining its goal. School heads should choose which instructional characteristics to examine and assess. The quality of education and student conduct are examples. School Heads may design an observation after determining its goal (Hong et al., 2020). This plan should contain the timing, number of observations, assessment criteria, and instructor input. Supervising classroom observation involves giving instructors feedback. These comments should be constructive and targeted to the instructor.

The practice of classroom observation among School Heads in DepEd-Ilocos Sur and DepEd Balanga City, has been a long-standing tradition. Supervision and monitoring of classrooms is an important part of school management, as it helps ensure that classroom instruction is effective and that students are learning. As such, School Heads in these two Divisions have been engaging in various supervision practices on classroom observation. The most observed practice is the informal classroom walk-through. This involves the school head visiting classrooms, without prior notice, to observe the teaching and learning activities of the class (Sakir & Kim, 2020). Often, these visits are brief and include talking to the teacher and students about the activity and offering feedback. This allows the school head to quickly identify any issues or problems that need to be addressed (Mkhwanazi et al., 2021). Another popular practice is the formal classroom observation. This entails scheduling a visit to a classroom, usually with prior notice, to observe the teacher and students in action (Perry et al., 2022).

Research on supervision practices on classroom observation among School Heads is still in its infancy. There is a lack of empirical evidence on the effectiveness of such practices in improving classroom instruction. Most of the research that has been conducted on the topic is based on surveys, interviews, or case studies. Little is known about the impact that different types of supervision practices can have on classroom instruction, or the extent to which they are utilized by School Heads. Furthermore, research into how School Heads use classroom observation as a tool for providing feedback to teachers and improving

instruction is limited. There is a lack of research into the factors that influence School Heads' decisions to either utilize or forego supervision practices on classroom observation. Such factors may include the School Heads' experience and knowledge, their philosophies about teaching and learning, and the school's overall culture. Finally, there is a need for research that examines the impact of classroom observation on student performance. This could include investigations into the relationship between classroom observation and student achievement or engagement.

Methodology

Research Design. The study adopted the mixed method design which included both qualitative and quantitative. In mixed methods design, the researchers gathered and analyzed quantitative and qualitative data with the intent of merging the findings of the analyses for both strands (Harrison et al., 2020). For this present study, the quantitative strand (QUAN) used a descriptive correlational approach, while the qualitative strand (QUAL) used a qualitative phenomenological approach.

Participants. The study recruited School Heads and Master Teachers in the Division of Ilocos Sur and Balanga City. They were recruited using random sampling. A total of 243 respondents for the quantitative approach and 20 participants for the qualitative approach.

Data Gathering Procedures and Ethical Considerations. Google Forms were used to create the survey's interactive interface. Participants from the two Divisions were sent through the link. Between the months of November and December of 2022, the survey URL may be accessed. The National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health Related Research, 2018 were followed in the design of this study (Philippine Health Ethics Board, 2018).

Data Analysis. The quantitative research topics were tested using statistical methods. The mean was used to evaluate the breadth of teaching methods. Pearson R was used to analyze the correlations between the variables. Thematic analysis was utilized on the qualitative data (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). The survey's free-form replies were reviewed and reread until their contents were fully understood. The stories were categorized using codes. Codes, classifications, and overarching themes evolved that completely characterized the phenomena. This study combined quantitative and qualitative methodologies, making full use of the strengths of each. To ensure the reliability of the study, the researcher used a simultaneous bidirectional technique (Johnson et al., 2020) in which the merging of data is defined by an interaction assessment of both emerging quantitative and qualitative outcomes.

Results and Discussion

The study presents the results of the data gathered from the respondents. It is divided into the quantitative strand, qualitative strand, and the integration of both quantitative and qualitative strand.

Quantitative Strand

Extent of Instructional Supervisory Practices. Table 1 presents the computed mean scores of the extent of instructional supervisory practices of School Heads and Master Teachers.

Table 1: Mean Scores of the Extent of Instructional Supervisory Practices of School Heads and Master Teachers

Indicators of Instructional Supervisory Practices	N	Mean	Interpretation
1. Instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation	254	3.74	Agree
2. Teachers' role effectiveness in lesson presentation	254	3.46	Agree
3. Teachers' role effectiveness in use of instructional materials	254	3.34	Agree

Results shows that School Heads and Master Teachers in the Division of Ilocos Sur and Balanga City often exhibited all the supervisory practices outlined in this study. This stems from the mean range of 3.74 and 3.46, and 3.34 obtained for all the three instructional supervisory practices. A 5-point Likert scale was used to collect data on instructional supervisory practices of headteachers. This implies a mean (average) score of 3.0. The inference is that School Heads and Master Teachers of the instructional supervisory tasks was above average for all the tasks. However, instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation among the School Heads and Master Teachers while provision of teacher’s role effectiveness in use of instructional materials was least practiced in the schools. It is important to note that School Heads and Master Teachers need to implement quality instructional practices. The findings of this study agree with those of Balyer and Ozcan (2020) that most of supervisors perform instructional supervisory practice on classroom observation. The finding further substantiates that of Mohd et al., (2020) that orientation of new teaching staff in their schools was dominant among Head Teachers.

Performance of the teachers as measured by their IPCRF. Results shows that majority (75.98 %) of the respondents have performed satisfactorily based on their IPCRF.

Table 2: Performance of the teachers as measured by their IPCRF.

Performance based on the IPCRF	N	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	254	37	14.57
Very Satisfactory	254	193	75.98
Satisfactory	254	24	9.45

This implies that a very satisfactory performance of teachers is that students are likely to receive a high-quality education, which will lead to better academic outcomes and improved life outcomes. Furthermore, the implication of teachers' very satisfactory performance is that students are receiving quality education, learning important skills, and gaining knowledge that will help them in their future academic and professional pursuits (Baber, 2020). It also means that educators are doing a good job of motivating and engaging students, creating an effective learning environment, and providing guidance and support when needed (Johnson, 2017).

Performance of the learners as measured by their general average in class. Results show that majority (67.71 %) of the respondents have performed satisfactorily based on their general average in class.

Table 3: Performance of Learners as Measured by their General Average in Class

Performance of Learners	N	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	254	16	6.29
Very Satisfactory	254	172	67.71
Satisfactory	254	13	5.12
Fairly Satisfactory	254	53	20.87

The implication of learners' very satisfactory performance in class is that they have a strong understanding of the material and concepts being taught and have demonstrated their ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired. This can lead to a greater level of confidence in their abilities and a greater sense of self-motivation to continue to strive for excellence in their studies. Furthermore, having a very satisfactory performance in class is that they are engaged, motivated, and eager to learn (Tambunan et al., 2021). This performance is likely to result in improved learning outcomes, greater academic success, and a positive attitude towards learning (Taipjutorus & Hansen, 2012).

Significant relationship between the extent of instructional supervisory practices and performance of teachers. Table 4 presents the significant relationships between the extent of instructional supervisory practices and performance of teachers.

Table 4: Significant Relationship between the Extent of Instructional Supervisory Practices and Performance of Teachers

	Domains of Instructional Supervisory Practices		
	Instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation	Teachers' role effectiveness in lesson presentation	Teachers' role effectiveness in use of instructional materials
r-value	0.229**	0.301**	0.259**
p-value	0.018	0.091	.001

Note: ** p < .01

Table 4 shows the Pearson R test results that determines the significance of the relationship between the domains of instructional supervisory practices and performance of teachers. Findings suggest that instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation (r=0.229; p=0.018), teachers' role effectiveness in lesson presentation (r=0.301; p<0.091) and teachers' role effectiveness in the use of instructional materials (r=0.259; p<0.001) had significant positive relationships with teachers' performance.

Significant relationship between the extent of instructional supervisory practices and performance of learners. Table 5 presents the significant relationships between the extent of instructional supervisory practices and performance of learners.

Table 5: Significant Relationship between the Extent of Instructional Supervisory Practices and Performance of Learners

	Domains of Instructional Supervisory Practices		
	Instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation	Teachers' role effectiveness in lesson presentation	Teachers' role effectiveness in use of instructional materials
r-value	0.219**	0.412**	0.256**
p-value	0.001	0.001	.001

Note: ** p < .01

Table 5 shows the Pearson R test results that determines the significance of the relationship between the domains of instructional supervisory practices and performance of teachers. Findings suggest that instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation (r=0.219; p=0.001), teachers' role effectiveness in lesson presentation (r=0.412; p<0.001) and teachers' role effectiveness in the use of instructional materials (r=0.256; p<0.001) had significant positive relationships with learners' performance.

The implication of a positive relationship between instructional supervisory practices and learners' performance is that when instructional supervisors provide support and guidance to learners, such as through providing feedback and guidance on their work, the learners are more likely to have better educational outcomes (Newman et al., 2021). This indicates that instructional supervisors play an important role in helping learners to achieve their learning goals and that instructional supervision is an effective tool for improving learning outcomes.

Moreover, instructional supervision can be an effective tool in improving learners' performance. By providing guidance, support and feedback to learners, instructional supervisors can help them build the skills and knowledge they need to be successful (Binu, 2021). This can lead to improved grades, more efficient learning, and increased confidence in their abilities.

Qualitative Strand

Lived Experiences of the instructional leaders towards quality basic education. From the data, six themes emerged from the narratives of the participants. These are (1) Student Engagement, (2) Teacher Professional Development, (3) Parent/Community Involvement, (4) Use of Technology, (5) Collaboration and Communication, and (6) Resource Allocation.

Theme 1: Student engagement. Many of the participants have indicated that an important practice towards quality basic education is student engagement. P01 explained the relevance of student engagement for quality basic education:

My experience with student engagement towards quality education has been overwhelmingly positive. I have seen students become highly motivated and engaged when given the opportunity to learn in an interactive and meaningful way.

On the other hand, P03 shared:

Student participation in excellent education has been really rewarding for me. I've seen kids work hard in class and participate in extracurriculars. They're eager to learn and like hard subjects. They also take responsibility for their learning and are innovative in discovering methods to improve.

Student engagement is a critical component of public-school systems as it directly supports the mission of providing quality education (Cholick & Samani, 2021). When students are actively engaged in their education, they are more motivated and committed to learning and are more likely to form meaningful relationships with their teachers which leads to improved academic success and improved communication which is essential for fostering a healthy learning environment.

Table 4: Themes depicting the experiences of Instructional leaders towards quality education

Themes	Participant Code	Sample Representative Code
Student Engagement	1	➤ My experience with student engagement towards quality education has been overwhelmingly positive. I have seen students become highly motivated and engaged when given the opportunity to learn in an interactive and meaningful way.
	3	➤ Student participation in excellent education has been really rewarding for me. I've seen kids work hard in class and participate in extracurriculars. They're eager to learn and like hard subjects.
Teacher Professional Development	7	➤ My experience with teacher professional development towards quality education has been very positive. I have seen teachers receive training on the latest teaching techniques and strategies, as well as the most up-to-date educational materials.
	10	➤ I have also seen teachers receive ongoing support from their colleagues and administrators, allowing them to stay current on the best practices for teaching and learning. This has led to an improved learning experience for students and better overall outcomes.
Parent/Community Involvement	2	➤ My experience with parent/community involvement towards quality education has been extremely positive. I have seen firsthand how parents, teachers, and community members can come together to create a learning environment that is engaging and stimulating.
	8	➤ Parent and community participation in schooling has been great for me. Parents, educators, and community leaders have worked together to expand student learning opportunities. They have donated finances, time, and

		resources to assist our children get the greatest education. This engagement is crucial to an effective and helpful learning environment.
Use of Technology	5	➤ Technology has improved schooling in my experience. I've seen technology engage kids, foster cooperation, and enrich learning. Technology may help teachers, students, and parents communicate, improving learning.
	9	➤ Technology has improved schooling for me. I think technology can help instructors develop compelling, interactive lessons. Technology has enabled virtual class discussions, collaborative projects, and access to resources for students.
Collaboration and Communication	7	➤ Great communication and teamwork for superb education. Collaboration and idea sharing may lead to creative education solutions. I've learned this via group initiatives and industry professionals.
	19	➤ Communication and teamwork with the goal of providing excellent education have been very rewarding for me. I've helped establish open lines of communication between classroom teachers, school officials, and parents to improve the school's ability to keep everyone participating in the decision-making process.
Resource Allocation	13	➤ Quality education resource allocation has been mostly favorable for me. I've witnessed how devoted teachers, administrators, and parents can work together to boost children' learning. I've witnessed how technology and materials can increase student education.
	20	➤ Excellent education has been well-resourced in my experience. I've witnessed resource allocation increase educational results and learning settings. I think resources should be utilized wisely to provide pupils the finest education.

Theme 2: Teacher professional development. Another emergent theme from the participants is their participation to teacher professional development. P07 shared:

My experience with teacher professional development towards quality education has been very positive. I have seen teachers receive training on the latest teaching techniques and strategies, as well as the most up-to-date educational materials.

Moreover, P10 added that:

I have also seen teachers receive ongoing support from their colleagues and administrators, allowing them to stay current on the best practices for teaching and learning. This has led to an improved learning experience for students and better overall outcomes.

Teacher professional development is an essential element of the public school system that helps to ensure that teachers are well-equipped to support the mission of quality education (Felayabi et al., 2022). It expands their knowledge and skills, creates engaging learning experiences for students which results to the enhancement of student achievement. Additionally, it can help teachers stay ahead of the curve when it comes to student learning, foster a sense of collaboration with regards to sharing of best practices.

Theme 3: Parent/community involvement. Another emergent theme from the participants is the involvement of parents and the members of the community. This is validated by the sharing of P07 and said:

My experience with parent/community involvement towards quality education has been extremely positive. I have seen firsthand how parents, teachers, and

community members can come together to create a learning environment that is both engaging and stimulating for students.

Moreover, P08 commented that:

Parent and community participation in schooling has been great for me. Parents, educators, and community leaders have worked together to expand student learning opportunities. They have donated finances, time, and resources to assist our children get the greatest education. This engagement is crucial to an effective and helpful learning environment.

The involvement of parents and community in public school system is paramount to supporting the mission of quality education. Their involvement is essential to ensure that the students receive quality education. They can also provide support for the school system in terms of resources, time, and financial contributions. Community members can likewise serve as mentors and role models for students, helping them to develop the skills necessary for success in the classroom. Furthermore, community members can offer extracurricular activities and opportunities for students to explore their interests, as well as to become more engaged in their education. Finally, parent and community involvement can help to foster a sense of community among public school stakeholders. By working together, parents and community members can create a supportive atmosphere that will foster a sense of pride and ownership in the public school system.

Theme 4: Use of technology. Another emergent theme from the participants is the utilization of technology towards instructional standards. This is validated by the sharing of P05 and said:

Technology has improved schooling in my experience. I've seen technology engage kids, foster cooperation, and enrich learning. Technology may help teachers, students, and parents communicate, improving learning.

Furthermore, P09 said:

Technology has improved schooling for me. I think technology can help instructors develop compelling, interactive lessons. Technology has enabled virtual class discussions, collaborative projects, and access to resources for students. I've also seen teachers utilize technology to test student knowledge and offer feedback swiftly and correctly.

The use of technology in public school systems is essential to support the mission of quality education. With technology, students are able to gain access to a wider range of resources and information, enabling them to learn more effectively. Technology also allows students to stay connected with their teachers and classmates outside of the classroom, allowing for more collaboration and engagement. It also allows teachers to better measure the progress of students, and facilitate administrative tasks, such as grading and attendance, making it easier for teachers to focus on what they do best which is teaching. Ultimately, technology can be used to provide enhanced learning opportunities for students. Educational software and apps can be used to supplement traditional teaching methods and give students access to more interactive, engaging activities.

Theme 5: Collaboration and communication. Another emergent theme from the narratives of the participants is collaboration and communication towards instructional standards. This is validated by the sharing of P07 and said:

Great communication and teamwork for superb education. Collaboration and idea sharing may lead to creative education solutions. I've learned this via group initiatives and industry professionals.

Likewise, P19 shared:

Communication and teamwork with the goal of providing excellent education have been very rewarding for me. I've helped establish open lines of communication between classroom teachers, school officials, and parents to improve the school's ability to keep everyone participating in the decision-making process.

Collaboration and communication are essential components of a successful public school system. When teachers collaborate and communicate effectively, they can share resources, best practices, and educational strategies. This allows them to develop innovative approaches to teaching and learning that can help students become more engaged in their education. Additionally, teachers can collaborate with each other to identify and address any issues that may arise in the classroom. Communication and collaboration are also important for involving parents in the educational process. By keeping parents informed about the school's activities and curriculum, they can become better informed and involved in their child's education. This can help create an environment where students feel supported, and their parents are invested in their education.

Theme 6: Resource allocation. Another emergent theme from the narratives of the participants is resource allocation towards instructional standards. This is validated by the sharing of P13 and said:

Quality education resource allocation has been mostly favorable for me. I've witnessed how devoted teachers, administrators, and parents can work together to boost children' learning. I've witnessed how technology and materials can increase student education.

In addition, in support of this theme, P20 said:

Excellent education has been well-resourced in my experience. I've witnessed resource allocation increase educational results and learning settings. I think resources should be utilized wisely to provide pupils the finest education.

Resource allocation in the public school system is an essential element of providing quality education to students. To ensure that students receive a quality education, it is important that resources are allocated efficiently and effectively. It helps determine needed resources, supports students through counseling and special education, and empowers educators through professional development. Proper allocation ensures access to textbooks, technology, and facilities such as libraries and laboratories, fostering an environment where students can excel.

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

From the direction of both quantitative and qualitative strand, it revealed three overarching themes: (1) seamless use of technology towards quality education, (3) performance is enhanced through professional development, and (3) teamwork from all stakeholders to support achievements for both teachers and learners.

Seamless use of technology towards quality education. Seamless use of technology in education can enhance the quality of education by providing students with more personalized learning experiences such as through the implementation of online courses and virtual classrooms. Online courses allow students

to learn at their own pace and on their own time, and virtual classrooms allow for a more interactive learning experience. Another way that technology can be used to enhance the quality of education is using artificial intelligence (AI). AI can be used to personalize the learning process and tailor it to each individual student's needs, to create sophisticated simulations and interactive experiences, and to facilitate collaboration and communication between students and their teachers. The widespread use of technological tools has unleashed a plethora of new avenues for scholastic development.

Performance is enhanced through professional development. Professional development for teachers is an important aspect of the teaching profession, as it can result in better overall performance in the classroom. Through professional development, teachers are given the opportunity to further their education and receive new knowledge and skills that can be applied to their teaching practice. It also gives teachers the opportunity to network with other professionals and help them to be abreast on the latest educational trends (Ha et al., 2020).

Teachers' effectiveness may be greatly improved by professional development programs that provide them with new skills and knowledge. It may also serve as a tool for them to learn about and implement the most cutting-edge strategies and techniques currently being used in the educational world. Teachers may benefit from professional development by learning strategies to enhance classroom management, which in turn can boost students' academic achievement (Matsko et al., 2020).

Teamwork from all stakeholders to support achievements for both teachers and learners. Teamwork is essential for any organization or group of people striving to achieve success. A team environment allows for a collective effort from all stakeholders to support the achievements of both teachers and learners in public schools. For teachers, teamwork helps to create a sense of camaraderie and increased job satisfaction. It can also encourage more effective learning by providing a platform for collaboration, discussion, and the sharing of ideas. By working together, teachers can create a positive learning atmosphere that is beneficial for students and encourages them to achieve their goals.

Conclusion

The role of instructional supervisory practices of School Heads and Master Teachers to the performance of teachers and learners is undeniable. Appropriate instructional supervisory practices have the potential to create a positive learning environment, facilitate teacher growth and development, and ultimately lead to improved student performance. For School Heads and Master Teachers, effective instructional supervision can help identify areas of improvement in teaching, provide feedback and constructive criticism to teachers, and motivate them to use effective teaching methods. Furthermore, instructional supervision can help teachers focus on the specific learning needs of their students, and to develop teaching strategies that target these needs. Ultimately, instructional supervisory practices of School Heads and Master Teachers can play a critical role in improving the performance of teachers and learners. The instructional supervision techniques of Principals and Master Teachers are crucial to the success of classroom instructors and students. The quality of education may be greatly enhanced via the use of such methods, which aid in providing direction, guidance, and support to educators and students alike. Such procedures have the potential to enhance classroom climate, lead to more organized lessons, and help teachers hone their craft. Further, they may facilitate an environment where both instructors and students feel comfortable sharing and building upon one another's ideas. Teachers and students both benefit from being held responsible for their actions, which may be achieved via the use of instructional supervisory procedures that promote this outcome. Ultimately, the success of both educators and students depends on the methods used by principals and Master Teachers for supervising classroom education.

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